

COMPREHENSIVE RENOVATION SOLUTIONS FOR UPGRADING EXISTING BUILDINGS TO NZEB LEVEL

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed within the project “Comprehensive Renovation Solutions for Upgrading Existing Buildings to nZEB Level”, implemented by Riga Technical University in cooperation with academic and industry partners. The project focuses on developing cost-optimized and technologically advanced solutions for the renovation of multi-apartment buildings, including energy-efficient HVAC systems, integration of renewable energy sources, prefabricated insulation technologies, and smart building systems to achieve nearly zero-energy building (nZEB) standards. The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all research data generated during the project are properly collected, documented, stored, secured, and, where appropriate, shared in accordance with the principles of Open Science and the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). The DMP also aims to ensure compliance with Latvia’s Open Science Strategy (2021–2027) and relevant EU requirements, while addressing issues related to data protection, intellectual property rights, and long-term preservation.

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European Regional
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Grant

Comprehensive Renovation
Solutions for Upgrading
Existing Buildings to nZEB Level

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Technical University, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: **COMPREHENSIVE RENOVATION SOLUTIONS FOR UPGRADING EXISTING BUILDINGS TO NZEB LEVEL**

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Organizations:

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University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Regional Development Fund

Grants: Comprehensive Renovation Solutions for Upgrading Existing Buildings to nZEB Level

Project: Comprehensive Renovation Solutions for Upgrading Existing Buildings to nZEB Level

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Venilation and IAQ measurements in a newly built aparatement

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset was generated to evaluate ventilation performance and indoor air quality (IAQ) in newly built apartments under realistic operating conditions. It supports the project's objective of assessing how different ventilation strategies influence IAQ indicators (e.g., CO₂ concentration, relative humidity, temperature, and moisture content) and occupant comfort.

The data enable a quantitative analysis of the impact of key factors such as occupancy levels, door position (open/closed), humidification, and ventilation system settings on IAQ. This provides evidence for optimizing ventilation design

and operation to ensure adequate air quality, energy efficiency, and compliance with relevant standards in modern residential buildings.

The data originate from field measurements carried out in residential apartments equipped with mechanical ventilation systems. Measurements were collected across multiple rooms (living room, bedroom, study room, and ventilation extract points) and under different ventilation scenarios (e.g., V70, Vmix, V113, V162). Environmental parameters were recorded using sensor-based monitoring, including CO₂ concentration, relative humidity, temperature, and moisture content, alongside contextual variables such as occupancy (0–2 persons), door status, and humidifier operation. The dataset consists of high-resolution time-series observations, enabling detailed analysis of IAQ dynamics under varying conditions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

60

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset may be useful for several stakeholder groups:

Researchers and academics in building science, ventilation, and indoor environmental quality, for analysing IAQ dynamics, validating models, and developing new ventilation strategies.

HVAC engineers and designers, to optimise ventilation system design and control strategies in residential buildings based on real performance data.

Policy makers and standardisation bodies, to support the development or revision of IAQ and ventilation requirements in building regulations.

Building developers and facility managers, to evaluate and improve the performance of ventilation systems in newly constructed apartments, ensuring occupant comfort and health.

Technology developers (sensor and smart control systems), for testing, calibration, and development of IAQ monitoring and demand-controlled ventilation solutions.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Indoor air quality (IAQ), Ventilation systems, Residential buildings, Mechanical ventilation, HVAC performance

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excell

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jurgis Zemitis (0000-0002-7812-3540)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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